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Synthesis of some New 1-Alkoxy-carbonyl-1-aryl/benzylsulphonyl-2-arylethylenes

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THE Knoevenagel condensations of the arylsulphonyl acetates unlike those of arylsulphonyl acetic acids, have not been extensively studied. Balasubramanian and Bahiah¹ have carried out the condensation by warming ethylphenylsulphonyl acetate (1; R=Ph, R'=Et) with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde in ethanol in presence of ammonium acetate. Following this procedure, Dressler and Grahm² condensed the same ester with

piperonal and anisaldehyde, and have characterized^{1,2} the products as 2.

In this communication, different sulphonyl acetates (1a, R=Ph, R'=Et; 1b, R=PhCH₂, R'=Et; 1c, R=PhCH₂, R'=Me; 1d, R=*p*-MeC₆H₄, R'=Et) were used for condensation in presence of ammonium acetate, ammonium carbonate, and ammonia solution³. However, under similar conditions, the condensation of 1a fails with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in presence of Triton-B, and anisaldehyde in presence of triethylamine⁴. Hence, these condensations may be described as Knoevenagel reaction⁴ proceeding via imine intermediate. The products were assigned as 2 on the basis of the elemental analyses and ir spectral data^{5,6} (Table 1).

It was observed that the treatment of the condensation product 2d with alcoholic ROH causes retro-Claisen change⁷ as reported by Chodroff and Whitmore⁷ for 2 (R=*n*-Bu, R'=Et).

Experimental

Condensation of sulphonyl acetates (1a-d) with aldehydes: To a solution of sulphonyl acetate (0.002 mol) and the aldehyde (0.002 mol) in dry ethanol (2-2.5 ml) was added the catalyst (0.002 mol dry ammonium acetate or ammonium carbonate or two drops of ammonia solution or 0.8 ml Triton-B). The reaction mixture was warmed, if necessary, to get a clear solution and finally kept overnight. The precipitate separated out on cooling in ice, was

TABLE 1—1-ALKOXYCARBONYL-1-ARYL/BENZYL SULPHONYL-2-ARYLETHYLENES*

Sl. no.	Sulphonyl ester	Aldehyde	Yield %	M.p. °C	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹
Catalyst: Ammonium acetate					
1.	a	<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	62.5-70.1	120-1	1 745, 1 645, 1 360, 1 150, 1 080
2.	a	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	61.7	125-6	1 740, 1 630, 1 365, 1 150, 1 080
3.	a	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	23.0	124	1 730, 1 640, 1 535, 1 360, 1 160, 1 090
4.	a	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde	43.0	186-8	—
5.	b	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	78.1	140-2	1 740, 1 645, 1 525, 1 350, 1 140
6.	b	Piperonal	—	Oily	1 735, 1 650, 1 350, 1 120
7.	c	Piperonal	66.8	129-80	—
8.	d	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	57.7-64.3	148-9	1 745, 1 645, 1 530, 1 350, 1 155, 1 090
9.	d	<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	51.0	100-1	1 740, 1 645, 1 350, 1 145, 1 090
Catalyst: Ammonium carbonate					
10.	a	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	58.5-71.7	171-2	1 740, 1 640, 1 520, 1 365, 1 150, 1 080
11.	a	<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	62.0	120-1	—
Catalyst: Ammonium hydroxide					
12.	a	<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	90.5	120-1	—

*All the compounds furnished satisfactory C (±0.32%) and H (±0.30%) analyses.

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filtered, crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b. p. 60–80°) mixture and characterised as 2 (Table 1).

Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss Specord 75 spectrophotometer.

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A Simple Method of Oximation. Transformation of Steroidal Nitroolefins to Ketoximes

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METHODS are reported for the transformation of nitroolefins into ketoximes^{1,2}. Some of these methods are rather drastic. This communication describes a simple method using methylamine, zinc dust for the conversion of 6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1), its 3 β -chloro (2) and 3 β -acetoxy analogues (3) into 5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (4), 3 β -chloro (5) and 3 β -acetoxy (6) ketoximes in 78–85% yields.

- 1, R=H
- 2, R=Cl
- 3, R=OAc

- 4, R=H
- 5, R=Cl
- 6, R=OAc

Experimental

To a well stirred solution of 6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) dissolved in ether-methanol (50 ml; 1:1) containing methylamine (15.0 ml, 40% in H₂O), zinc dust (3.0 g) was added at room temperature. The change of colour in ~1 h indicated the completion of the reaction and was also monitored by tlc. The reaction mixture was filtered into a separating funnel containing water and washed with water several times. The ethereal solution was dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous) and evaporated. The semi-solid thus obtained was re-crystallised to give 5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (4) (780 mg, 78%), m.p. 197° (lit⁶. 197–98°). Under similar reaction conditions, nitroolefins 2 and 3 provided ketoximes 5 (800 mg, 80%), m.p. 173° (lit⁶. 175°) and 6 (850 mg, 85%), m.p. 200° (lit⁷. 201°).

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Condensed 1,8-Naphthyridines. Part-VII.

Synthesis of 6H-Indeno[1,2-b][1,8]-naphthyridin-6-one

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of 2,3 fused^{1–4} and substituted^{5–7} 1,8-naphthyridines, we report in this note the synthesis of the hitherto unreported 6H-indeno[1,2-b][1,8]naphthyridin-6-one.

The starting compound 2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid (I) was obtained by the alkaline hydrolysis of 3-cyano-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine, which in turn obtained by the condensation